

DIGITALIZATION OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The article contains information about the reforms implemented in the higher education system of Uzbekistan and the prospects of digitalization of higher education. The implementation of the credit-module system in the educational process of higher education and the role of independent education in it, the importance and necessity of using telecommunications educational materials based on digital technologies in the organization of independent education are based. The content of telecommunication educational projects and the methodology and stages of effective organization of telecommunication projects in the educational process of higher education are presented.*

Key words: *technology, independent education, project method, telecommunications, educational projects, integration.*

INTRODUCTION

Systematic and consistent reforms in the field of education in our country are showing their results, our universities have achieved academic and financial independence, have the ability to define their goals and tasks, adapt to the requirements of the times, and train highly qualified personnel for today and the future [1]. One of the main tasks in the development of higher education and taking a worthy place in the international education system is the extensive development of the process of digitalization of the education system. Digitization has created new opportunities for learning and management, facilitating data collection and analysis, collaboration and communication. The benefits of digitization include increased productivity, increased student engagement, personalized learning, and the use of new teaching methods. In addition, digitization facilitates the management of universities, curricula, faculty, staff, and resources [1].

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Pedagogical observation, comparative analysis, generalization, pedagogical experiment-test, mathematical-statistical analysis, mental cards, expert survey of foresight, development of scenarios, future box, and Delphi methods were used in the research process.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The introduction of the credit-module system in the higher education system of Uzbekistan from the 2019-2020 academic year necessitated the radical redevelopment of the curricula of educational areas and master's specialties. In the current credit-module system, 50-60% of the total educational load allocated to the major subjects in the curriculum of bachelor's education courses, and about 60-70% in the master's specializations are allocated to independent education. However, independent education is mainly carried out by preparing abstracts on the topic or giving tasks to summarize the topic. Writing an annotation or review on the topic can be added to this, and this will at least guide students to independent creative thinking. These traditional methods are outdated and do not work well in the innovative educational environment. Therefore, the author recommends the organization of independent education in science using the method of design [2] on the basis of digital technologies, that is, "Telecommunication educational projects" [3].

Telecommunication projects appeared in developed foreign countries in the 80s of the last century and began to be used as a convenient and fast way of communication in the fields of science and education [4]. International experience shows that compared to simple correspondence-based telecommunication projects, specially organized and targeted projects, students' cooperation on the Internet lead to a great pedagogical result. Educational telecommunication projects are the main form of organizing joint educational activities of students of different cities, regions and countries in the network [5,6].

Telecommunication training projects are not televised training. Educational telecommunication projects are considered digital technologies organized on the basis of computers through Internet networks and occupy an important place in the innovative educational environment. Information exchange in educational telecommunication projects is carried out in written form. This allows students to think well about their thoughts, edit them, and plays a positive role in their cognitive activity and the formation of a culture of communication [7].

Telecommunication projects can be organized within the framework of a higher education institution, together with higher education institutions within the state, or in the form of an international project with partner foreign higher education institutions

[8]. This project is also of social importance, and has its place not only in education, but also in the field of education, that is, students working in the project are able to understand each other, respect the opinions of others, express their opinions freely. they learn to communicate and solve problems together. In particular, it is necessary to take into account the national and ethnic, socio-cultural values and respect them when the projects are organized with the partner higher educational institutions of the higher education system of Uzbekistan.

The application of this project to the educational process, firstly, increases the quality of independent education, and secondly, the project creates conditions for entering the field of international education and working in cooperation with foreign students. Problem solving in telecommunication educational projects requires integrated knowledge. Especially in international projects, it requires a deeper integration of knowledge, not only the field of scientific knowledge related to the researched problem, but also the characteristics of the partner's national culture, his knowledge and understanding of the world, and his views.

This constitutes a culture of dialogue. Currently, the professor of the University of Illinois, Ohio, USA, V. Heathergood, has been leading the network project for many years, and young people from about 40 countries participate in it. International projects based on the Kidlink program and the I Earm program are working on the Internet [9]. The main obstacle for students to participate in international telecommunications educational projects is the level of knowledge of a foreign language.

Telecommunication educational projects appeared in the 80s of the last century and are used as a convenient and fast way of communication in the fields of science and education. International experience shows that compared to simple correspondence-based telecommunication projects, specially organized and targeted projects, students' cooperation on the Internet lead to a great pedagogical result. Educational telecommunication projects are the main form of organizing joint educational activities of students from different cities, regions and countries. Such international projects include "Shakespeare Seminars" which have been organized for more than ten years by Professor V. Heathergood of the University of Illinois at Ohio State through the IEARN (<http://www.iearn.org>) and KIDLINK (<http://www.kidlink.org>) programs. can be used as an example. Young people from about 40 countries will participate in it. It is possible to use hidden coordination in regional or international telecommunication projects, that is, the coordinator or one of the coordinators, as a participant of the project, sends the work (task) to the participants of the "hidden" project [10].

Educational telecommunication projects are educational, research, creative, scientific and playful activities of student-partners, organized on the basis of computer telecommunication, having a common problem, goal, agreed methods and methods of activity, and directed to achieving a joint result of the activity. Problem solving in any project requires integrated knowledge. In order to effectively organize telecommunication projects in the educational process of higher education, the following should be taken into account [11]:

- multiple, systematic, one-time or long-term observation of natural, physical, social and other phenomena to solve the given problem, collecting data from different regions;
- comparative study, making decisions and developing proposals to determine the exact trend of events, evidence, events occurring in different places;
- to compare and study the effectiveness of ways to solve a problem or issue (alternative or different methods), taking into account the differences between the cultural, ethnic, geographical conditions of the project participants;
- comparative analysis of social and cultural views, taking into account specific cultural, traditional, religious features;
- development of a creative idea (practical, creative, scientific, etc.) under the condition of joint research of a specific problem;
- conducting interesting adventure computer games and competitions, and focusing on the problem situations that arise in the context of cultural, educational traditions, sports.

CONCLUSION

A telecommunication project, especially international projects, requires a deeper integration of knowledge, not only the field of scientific knowledge related to the researched problem, but also the characteristics of the partner's national culture, his knowledge and understanding of the world, his views. This will increase the culture of dialogue. For telecommunication projects organized in a foreign language (if specified in the program), it is considered appropriate to organize oral speech and reading development courses in foreign languages in accordance with the content and content of the project. If such projects are organized from special subjects or general professional subjects, and the problem texts in it do not correspond to the foreign language program, they can be organized personally (individually) during extracurricular time. It is known that information exchange in telecommunication projects is carried out in written form. This allows students to think well about their thoughts, edit them, and plays a positive role in their cognitive activity and the formation of social culture. In this project, the main condition or obstacle is the level

of knowledge of a foreign language [12]. Therefore, Decision PQ-1875 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" is a timely decision, and all aimed at creating sufficient conditions for teachers and students in schools.

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